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LIBARCCLIENT

A Client Library for ARC

KnowARC

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Chapter 1

Preface

This document describes from a technical viewpoint a plugin-based client library for the new Web Service (WS) based Advanced Resource Connector [9] (ARC) middleware. The library consists of a set of C++ classes for

- handling proxy, user and host certificates,
- performing computing resource discovery and information retrieval,
- filtering and brokering of found computing resources,
- job submission and management and
- data handling.

All capabilities are enabled for three different grid flavours (Production ARC, Web Service ARC and gLite [1]) through a modular design using plugins specialized for each supported middleware. Future extensions to support additional middlewares involve plugin compilation only i.e., no recompilation of main libraries or clients is necessary.

Using the library, a set of command line tools have been built which puts the library's functionality at the fingertips of users. This documentation is not intended to document the developed CLI but the concept of how to build command line tools will be demonstrated. Readers interested in the user interface are recommended to read the client user manual [8].

Chapter 2

Functionality Overview

The new libarcclient makes extensive use of plugins for command handling. These plugins are handled by a set of higher level classes which thus are the ones to offer the plugin functionality to external calls. In this section an overview of the library's main functionality is given which also introduces the most important higher level classes. Readers interested in the library API are recommended to look up the online API documentation [3].

2.1 Resource Discovery and Information Retrieval

With the increasing number of grid clusters around the world, a reliable and fast resource discovery and information retrieval capability is of crucial importance for a user interface. The new libarcclient resource discovery and information retrieval component consists of three classes; the `TargetGenerator`, the `TargetRetriever` and the `ExecutionTarget`. Of these the `TargetRetriever` is a base class for further grid middleware specific specialization (plugin).

Figure 2.1 depicts how the classes work together in a command chain to discover all resources registered with a certain information server. Below a description of each step is given:

1. The `TargetGenerator` takes three arguments as input. The first argument is a reference to a `UserConfig` object containing a representation of the contents of the user's configuration file. The second and third arguments contain lists of strings. The first list contains individually selected and rejected computing services, while the second list contains individually selected and rejected index servers. Rejected servers and services are identified by that its name is prefixed by a minus sign in the lists. The name of the servers and services should be given either in the form of an alias defined in the `UserConfig` object or as the name of its grid flavour followed by a colon and the URL of its information contact endpoint.
2. These lists are parsed through alias resolution before being used to initialize the complete list of selected and rejected URLs pointing to computing services and index servers.
3. For each selected index server and computing service a `TargetRetriever` plugin for the server's or service's grid flavour is loaded using the ARC loader. The `TargetRetriever` is initialized with its URL and the information about whether it represents a computing service or an index server.
4. An external call is received calling for targets to be prepared. The call for targets is processed by each `TargetRetriever` in parallel.
5. A `TargetRetriever` representing an index server first tries to register at the index server store kept by the `TargetGenerator`. If allowed to register, the index server is queried and the query result processed. The `TargetGenerator` will not allow registrations from index servers present in its list of rejected index servers or from servers that have already registered once. Index servers often register at more than one index server, thus different `TargetRetrievers` may discover the same server.
6. If while processing the query result the `TargetRetriever` finds another registered index server or a registered computing service it creates a new `TargetRetriever` for the found server or service and forwards the call for targets to the new `TargetRetriever`.

Figure 2.1: Diagram depicting the resource discovery and information retrieval process

7. A **TargetGenerator** representing a computing service first tries to register at the service store kept by the **TargetGenerator**. If allowed to register, the computing server is queried and the query result processed. The **TargetGenerator** will not allow registrations from computing services present in its list of rejected computing services or from service that have already registered once. Computing services often register at more than one index server, thus different **TargetRetrievers** may discover the same service.
8. When processing the query result the **TargetRetriever** will create an **ExecutionTarget** for each queue found on the computing service and collect all possible information about them. It will then store the **ExecutionTarget** in the found targets store kept by the **TargetGenerator** for later usage (e.g. status printing or job submission).

2.2 Job Submission

Job submission starts with the resource discovery and target preparation as outlined in the Section 2.1. Not until a list of possible targets (which authorize the user) is available is the job description read in order to enable bulk job submission of widely different jobs without having to reperform the resource discovery. In addition to the classes mentioned above the job submission makes use of the **Broker**, **JobDescription** and **Submitter** classes. The **Submitter** is base class for further grid middleware specific specialization (plugin) similarly to the **TargetRetriever**.

Figure 2.2 shows a job submission sequence and below a description of each step is given:

1. The **TargetGenerator** has prepared a list of **ExecutionTargets**. Depending on the URLs provided to the **TargetGenerator** the list of found **ExecutionTargets** may be empty or contain several targets. Targets may even represent more than one grid flavour. The list of found targets are given as input to the **Broker**.

Figure 2.2: Diagram depicting the submission of a job to a computing service.

2. In order to rank the found services (**ExecutionTargets**) the **Broker** needs detailed knowledge about the job requirements, thus the **JobDescription** is passed as input to the brokering process.
3. The **Broker** filters and ranks the **ExecutionTargets** according to the ranking method chosen by the user.
4. Each **ExecutionTarget** has a method to return a specialized **Submitter** which is capable of submitting jobs to the service it represents. The best suitable **ExecutionTarget** for the job is asked to return a **Submitter** for job submission.
5. The **Submitter** takes the **JobDescription** as input and uploads it to the computing service.
6. The **Submitter** identifies local input files from the **JobDescription** and uploads them to the computing service.

2.3 Job Management

Once a job is submitted, job related information (job identification string, cluster etc.) is stored in a local XML file which stores this information for all active jobs. This file may contain jobs running on completely different grid flavours, and thus job management should be handled using plugins similar to resource discovery and job submission. The job managing plugin is called the **JobController** and it is supported by the **JobSupervisor** and **Job** classes.

Figure 2.3 shows how the three different classes work together and below a step by step description is given:

1. The **JobSupervisor** takes four arguments as input. The first argument is a reference to a **UserConfig** object containing a representation of the contents of the user's configuration file. The second is a list of strings containing job identifiers and job names, the third is a list of strings of clusters to select or

Figure 2.3: Diagram depicting how job controlling plugins, JobControllers, are loaded and initialized.

reject (in the same format as described for the `TargetGenerator` above). The last argument is the name of the file containing the local information about active jobs, hereafter called the joblist file.

- A job identifier does not uniquely define which grid flavour runs a certain job. Thus this information is stored in the joblist file upon submission by the `Submitter` and the joblist file is extensively used by the `JobSupervisor` to identify the `JobController` flavours which are to be loaded. The information in the joblist file is also used to look up the job identifier for jobs specified using job names. Alias resolving for the selected and rejected clusters are performed using the information in the `UserConfig` object.
- Suitable `JobControllers` are loaded
- The list of job identifiers and selected and rejected clusters are passed to each `JobController` which uses the information to fill its internal `JobStore`.
- Residing within the `JobSupervisor` the `JobControllers` are now accessible for external calls (i.e. job handling).

Chapter 3

The ARC Brokering Module

The ARC brokering module is made up of two kinds of classes: one brokering base class and specialized classes derived thereof. The brokering base class which implements the method for reducing a list of resources found by resource discovery (the list of `ExecutionTargets` residing within the `TargetGenerator`) to a list of resources capable of running a certain job:

```
void PreFilterTargets(const TargetGenerator& targeten, const JobDescription& jd);
```

The `PreFilterTargets` method compares every hardware and software requirement given in the job description against the computing resource (cluster) specifications stored in the `ExecutionTarget`. If the `ExecutionTarget` doesn't fulfil the requirements imposed by the job description, or it is impossible to carry out the match-making due to incomplete information published by the computing resource, the `ExecutionTarget` will be removed from the list of possible targets.

Once prefiltered, the remaining `ExecutionTargets` should be ranked in order to return the “best” `ExecutionTarget` for job submission. Different ranking methods are implemented by the specialized brokers, but for usability and consistency reasons these methods are encapsulated by the `Broker` base class method

```
ExecutionTarget& GetBestTarget(bool &EndOfList);
```

which invokes the `SortTargets` method implemented by the specialized broker (see Section 3.1) and returns the best target. The `GetBestTarget` method is “incremented” at each call, thus upon a second call the second best `ExecutionTarget` will be returned.

3.1 Broker plugins

Random

The `Random` ranks the `ExecutionTargets` randomly.

3.1.1 Benchmark

The `Benchmark` ranks the `ExecutionTargets` according to their benchmark performance. Through the command line tool (see the user manual[8] for reference) this specialized broker takes a user specified benchmark as input and ranks the `ExecutionTargets` according to their published benchmark performance. If

no benchmark is specified the CINT2000 (Integer Component of SPEC CPU2000)* benchmark is used as default.

3.1.2 FastestQueueBroker

The `FastestQueueBroker` ranks the `ExecutionTargets` according to their queue length measured in percentage of the `ExecutionTarget`'s size (i.e. the queue length divided by the number of total slots/CPUs). If more than one `ExecutionTarget` has zero queue, the `FastestQueueBroker` makes use of a basic load balancing method to rearrange the zero queue `ExecutionTargets` depending on their number of free slots/CPUs.

3.1.3 Data

The `Data` ranks the `ExecutionTargets` according to how many megabytes of the requested input files that already stored in the cache of the computing resource the `ExecutionTarget` represents. The broker is motivated by that jobs should be submitted to `ExecutionTargets` where the data already is, thus reducing the network load on both the computing resource and client side. The ranking method is based upon the A-REX[†] interface `CacheCheck` for querying for the presence of the file in the cache directory. This interface has a limitation in the current implementation and does not support per user caches.

The `SortTargets` method has four steps:

1. Only the A-REX service has `CacheCheck` method, thus `ExecutionTargets` not running A-REX are removed.
2. Information about input files requested in the job description is collected from the `JobInnerRepresentation`.
3. Each `ExecutionTarget` is queried (through the `CacheCheck` method) for the existence of input files. A single query is used for achieving all the necessary information and file sizes are summarized. If there are problems determining file sizes, then the summarized size will be zero.
4. The possible `ExecutionTargets` are ranked in a descending order according to the amount of input data they have in their cache.

Example of a `CacheCheck` request that can be sent to an A-REX service:

```
<CacheCheck>
  <TheseFilesNeedToCheck>
    <FileURL>http://example.org/storage/Makefile</FileURL>
    <FileURL>ftp://download.nordugrid.org/test/README</FileURL>
  </TheseFilesNeedToCheck>
</CacheCheck>
```

Example `CacheCheck` response from the A-REX service:

```
<CacheCheckResponse>
  <CacheCheckResult>
    <Result>
      <FileURL>http://example.org/storage/Makefile</FileURL>
      <ExistInTheCache>true</ExistInTheCache>
      <FileSize>190</FileSize>
```

*<http://www.spec.org/cpu2000/CINT2000/>

†http://www.knowarc.eu/download/D1.2-3_documentation.pdf

```

</Result>
<Result>
  <FileURL>ftp://download.nordugrid.org/test/README</FileURL>
  <ExistInTheCache>true</ExistInTheCache>
  <FileSize>176</FileSize>
</Result>
</CacheCheckResult>
</CacheCheckResponse>

```

3.1.4 PythonBroker

This `PythonBroker` allows users to write their customized broker in python. To use this broker the user should write a python class which should contain:

- an `__init__` method that takes a `Config` object as input, and
- a `SortTargets` method that takes a python list of `ExecutionTarget` objects and a `JobInnerRepresentation` object as input.

The `Config`, `ExecutionTarget` and `JobInnerRepresentation` classes are available in the swig generated arc python module.

To invoke the `PythonBroker`, the name of the python module defining the broker class and the name of the broker class must be given. If e.g. the broker class `MyBroker` is defined in the python module `SampleBroker` the command line option to `arcsb` to use this broker is:

```
-b PythonBroker:SampleBroker.MyBroker
```

Additional arguments to the python broker can be added by appending them after an additional colon after the python class name:

```
-b PythonBroker:SampleBroker.MyBroker:args
```

Extracting these additional arguments should be done in the python broker class's `__init__` method.

For a complete example of a simple python broker see the `SampleBroker.py` file that comes with your arc python installation.

Chapter 4

Job Description

Since new WS-ARC utilizes a middleware plugin structure, it also need to support the various job description languages used by these middlewares. Therefore the JSDL, XRSL and JDL job description languages are supported. In order to provide support for the three languages listed above, an internal job description data structure is needed which is the union of the supported languages. The internal job description data structure of new WS-ARC is described in a separate document, the ARC Job Description Internal Representation [2].

Chapter 5

Grid Flavour Plugins and Commons

With a library utilizing plugins a mapping to a common set of job states is needed in order to be able to treat jobs from different middlewares in the same way. In WS-ARC the following job states comprises the state model which plugins should map their job states:

UNDEFINED Job state could not be resolved,

ACCEPTED Job was accepted by the service,

PREPARING Job is preparing,

SUBMITTING Job is being submitted to a computing share,

HOLD Job is put on hold,

QUEUEING Job is on computing share waiting to run,

RUNNING Job is running on computing share,

FINISHING Job is finishing,

FINISHED Job has finished,

KILLED Job has been killed,

FAILED Job failed,

DELETED Job have been deleted,

OTHER Any job state which does not fit the above states.

See Appendix B for the actual job state mapping of each of the below described plugins

5.1 ARC0 Plugins

The ARC0 plugins enables support for the interfaces used by computing elements running ARC version 0.x.

The ARC 0.x local information system uses the Globus Toolkit[®] [10] GRIS with a custom made ARC schema. The information index server used is the Globus Toolkit[®] GIIS. Both these servers use the LDAP [14] protocol. The specialization of the **TargetRetriever** class for ARC0 is implemented using the ARC LDAP Data Management Component (DMC) (see [7] for technical details).

Jobs running on an ARC 0.x computing element are handled by the ARC grid-manager [13]. Job submission and job control are done using the gridftp [5] protocol. The specializations of the **Submitter** and **JobController** classes use the globus ftp control library.

Stage-in and stage-out of input and output files are also done using the gridftp [5] protocol. This means that proper functionality of the ARC0 plugins requires the gridftp DMC.

5.2 ARC1 Plugins

The computing element in ARC version 1.x is the A-Rex [12] service running in a HED [7] container.

A-Rex implements the BES [11] standard interface. Since this is a SOAP-based [6] interface, the specializations of the `TargetRetriever`, `Submitter` and `JobController` classes make use of a chain of ARC Message Chain Components (MCC [7]) ending with the SOAP client MCC.

The A-Rex service uses the https protocol `put` and `get` methods for stage-in and stage-out of input and output files. Therefore, the ARC1 plugins requires the http DMC.

5.3 gLite Plugins

The gLite computing element offers several interfaces, one of them being the Web Service based computing element interface known as the CREAM CE [4]. The current revision of this interface (CREAM version 2) has been chosen for implementation within libarcclient for the following reasons:

- CREAM2 has a Web Service interface that is very similar to the Web Service based ARC.
- CREAM2 enables direct access to the gLite computing element without having to go via the gLite workload management system.
- CREAM2 contains numerous improvements when compared to the earlier CREAM versions.
- CREAM2 supports direct job status queries.
- CREAM2 offers a convenient way of handling input and output files through accessing the input and output sandbox via GridFTP.

gLite resources are registered in top level and site BDII's. The CREAM specialization of the `TargetRetriever` therefore makes use of the LDAP DMC similarly to the ARC0 plugins.

CREAM has its own SOAP-based interface. The CREAM specializations of the `Submitter` and `JobController` classes therefore use an MCC chain ending with the SOAP client MCC the same way the ARC1 plugin does.

Stage-in and stage-out of input and output files are done using the gridftp protocol. The gridftp DMC is therefore required.

Appendix A

ExecutionTarget

<http://svn.nordugrid.org/trac/nordugrid/browser/arc1/trunk/doc/client/ExecutionTargetMapping.html>

Appendix B

Job Status mapping

Internal	ARC0	ARC1	BES	CREAM
ACCEPTED	ACCEPTED	ACCEPTED	Pending	REGISTERED, PENDING
PREPARING	PREPARING	PREPARING	None	None
SUBMITTING	SUBMIT	SUBMIT	None	None
HOLD	None	None	None	HELD
QUEUING	INLRMS:Q	INLRMS:Q	None	IDLE
RUNNING	INLRMS:R	INLRMS:R, INLRMS:EXECUTED, INLRMS:S, INLRMS:E	Running	RUNNING, REALLY-RUNNING
FINISHING	FINISHING	FINISHING	None	None
FINISHED	FINISHED	FINISHED	Finished	DONE-OK
KILLED	KILLED	KILLED	None	CANCELLED
FAILED	FAILED	FAILED	Failed	DONE-FAILED, ABORTED
DELETED	DELETED	DELETED	None	None
OTHER	Any other state	Any other state	None	Any other state

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